

Organisation [University of Évora]
Department [Renewable Energies Chair]

Deliverable 4.1

Regional, National and International Fora Report

Sol2H2O

Date: 03.07.2025

Doc. Version: 1

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Document Title:	Regional, National and International Fora Report
Project Title:	Sol2H2O
Document Author:	Dominique Livreiro, Pedro Horta, Nunzio Cancilla
Project Owner:	European Commission
Project Manager:	Pedro Horta (UEVORA)
Doc. Version:	1
Sensitivity:	Public
Date:	03.07.2025

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date
Pedro Horta (UEVORA)	PM	<i>Accepted</i>	28.07.2025
Guillermo Zaragoza (CIEMAT)	PSC	<i>Accepted</i>	30.07.2025
Juan Antonio Bencomo (ITC)	PSC	<i>Accepted</i>	29.07.2025
Andrea Cipollina (UNIPA)	PSC	<i>Accepted</i>	29.07.2025

Document history:

The Document Author is authorised to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarised in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in *project folder*.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of Sol2H2O¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D4.1 - Regional, National and International Fora Report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

D4.1 is a report on the implementation and measurable impacts of the Regional Specialization Fora, Water-Energy Strategy Symposium and Water-Energy Transition Symposium, activities that actively disseminate the cross-cutting Sol2H2O outcomes among industrial partners and other stakeholders, enhancing the development of a common policy alignment on Solar-driven water production and zero-liquid discharge solutions, and solar-driven wastewater treatment at different political and geographical levels (Task 4.1, WP4).

Designed as measures to maximize Sol2H2O's impact at the 4Helix level: Academia, Policy Makers, Industry, and Civil Society, these events foster the project's outreach at regional (Regional Specialization Fora), national (Water-Energy Strategy Symposium) and international levels (Water-Energy Transition Symposium), as taken from the perspective of the Widening partner: national and regional levels refer to the widening partner, UÉvora, thus referring to Portugal and the Alentejo region; the international level, on the other hand, allowed for the participation of stakeholders from the Consortium countries, implying the presence of participants from Portugal, Italy and Spain.

These events follow one of Sol2H2O's objective 4. To enhance the networking of UÉvora in scientific and Industry fora, by means of disseminating the Widening RI services among Industry, and two more events, beyond those planned for the project, were organised: a Regional Specialization Forum in Palermo and a National Water Energy Strategy Symposium in Italy.

2. REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION FORA

Aiming at the engagement of relevant stakeholders, to Sol2H2O's objectives, 4-Helix stakeholders at the regional level, the Regional Specialization Fora (RSF) were designed as a periodic event engaging Policy, Industry and Academia around the role of Sol2H2O technological solutions in the objectives of the Regional Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3).

This event was foreseen to take place every 6 months, with a total of 5 events along the project, in M6, M12, M18, M24 and M30. Due to technical-administrative constraints, the first RSF was organised in M11, and 4 editions have already been held (RSF#4 was held together with the Water-Energy Strategy Symposium to promote more participation of regional actors), being RSF#5 planned for September 2025 (M34).

Beyond the foreseen Regional Specialization Fora at the Widening partner's location, in view of the pressing interest in alternative water resources in Sicily, an additional RSF edition took place in Palermo, in April'24.

With a first edition aimed at presenting the project scope and technological solutions, these Fora fostered a continued discussion, with the participants, on the potential of Sol2H2O technologies for the region, the possible role of regional industry in their development and the potential impact of both technology use and production in the RIS3 and in the regional development strategy.

Though the audience kept rising from each RSF event, it became clear that there is a lack of regional stakeholders in Sol2H2O's technological field. In fact, and being an essentially agrarian region, besides some industrial capabilities existing in the sole relevant industrial pole in the region - the petrochemical complex in Sines - developing activities and presenting competencies not directly related to Sol2H2O JRA scope, the level of success of these initiatives, when measured by the target audiences sought in the proposal, revealed to be modest.

¹ Project: 101079305 — Sol2H2O — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

Table 2.1 summarises the number of participants in the RSF events and their level of success.

Table 2.1: Number of participants in RFS#1 to #4 and RSF Palermo, and level of success (KPI)

Regional Specialization Forum	Level of Success	New external Registrations*	External participants registration**	Total registrations
RSF#1	Good: 15-25 registrations	9	9	15
RSF#2		8	13	19
RSF#3	Very Good: 26-40 registrations	2	5	13
RSF#4	Excellent: >40 registrations	7	12	20
RSF Palermo		84	84	100

* New external participants in each event

** Participants not affiliated with any of the Sol2H2O Consortium partners

The stark difference in attendance between the Widening partner RSF editions and the RSF edition in Palermo illustrates the current pressure on water resources in Sicily.

Regarding the initially foreseen RSF editions in the Widening context, the distribution of external participants, in each of the 4 RSF editions, by type of actor is presented in the graphic of Figure 2.1. The percentage distribution of actors in the 4 RSF editions already completed is presented in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.1: RSF audience by type of actor and RSF edition

Figure 2.2: Percentage distribution of actor types among the overall audience of the 4 RSF editions already completed

Both announcements and news about the RSF editions were published on Sol2H2O communication channels (social media, newsletter and website, Figure 2.3), and the presentations are available on Sol2H2O Zenodo and website: <https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/media-en/#presentations>.

Figure 2.3. RSF#1 announcement on Sol2H2O LinkedIn

A description of each of the RSF editions follows.

2.1. RSF #1

The first edition of RSF took place in Évora, on the 31st of October 2023 (M11), in the CCDR Alentejo (Regional Coordination and Development Commission) installations (Figure 2.1.1). With a total of 15 participants (9 external to the Sol2H2O team, being 3 from the Industry, 1 from Civil Society, 1 from the Academia, and 4 from the Policy sector - Appendix 2), the event started with a presentation of Sol2H2O and its technological solutions (dessalination and wastewater

treatment areas), as well as the relationship with EREI (Regional Strategy for Smart Specialisation) Alentejo 2030 and the regional potential.

Figure 2.1.1. RSF#1 (October 2023)

2.2. RSF #2

The second edition of RSF took place in Évora, on the 18th of April 2024 (M17), in the CCDR Alentejo (Regional Coordination and Development Commission) installations (Figure 2.2.1). With a total of 19 participants (13 external to the Sol2H2O team, being 3 from the Industry and 8 new external participants - Appendix 2), the event started with a review of the Sol2H2O technology, Integrated Territorial Instrument, value chains and regional potential, and new projects for the UÉvora Sol2H2O team.

Figure 2.2.1. RSF#2 (April 2024)

2.3. RSF #3

The third edition of RSF took place in Évora, on the 21st of June 2024 (M18), in the auditorium of the University of Évora (Figure 2.3.3). With a total of 13 participants (5 external to the Sol2H2O team, and 2 were new participants regarding the previous editions - Appendix 2), the event started with an overview of the Sol2H2O ongoing tasks and other ongoing projects related to the same technological topics. These participants were also invited to visit the UÉvora Research Infrastructure, in Herdade da Mitra, together with the SALTOpower RSF#3 participants (as UÉvora coordinates both Horizon Europe Twinning Projects), and the XIX Iberian Congress and XV Ibero-American Congress on Solar Energy (CIES'24) participants, organised by UÉvora in the previous days.

Figure 2.3.3. RSF#3 (June 2024)

2.4. RSF #4

The fourth edition of RSF took place in Évora, on the 6th of February 2025 (M27), in Casa Cordovil, University of Évora (Figure 2.4.1), along with the Water-Energy Strategy Symposium, a debate on the regional strategy was held. A total of 20 regional participants (12 external to the Sol2H2O team, and 7 being new participants regarding the previous editions - Appendix 2) were present in both events, which also included a visit to Herdade da Mitra to visit the Sol2H2O Research Infrastructure.

Figure 2.4.1. RSF#4 (February 2025)

2.5. RSF #5

In view of the adhesion results gathered in the previous editions of the RSF, the fifth edition will be replaced by a more effective, national wide event in September 2025 (M34), along with the Sol2H2O participation in the 3rd Energy and Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show (ENERH2O). Moreover, a wider scope roadshow of UEvora infrastructure, including Sol2H2O pilot and JRA activities, is under discussion, to be organized as a national scope event within the end of October'25.

2.6. RSF Palermo

Another Regional Specialization Forum was organized by UNIPA and took place at the University of Palermo (Figure 2.6.1) on the 3rd and 4th of April 2024, with the attendance of about one hundred participants (the attendance list is provided in Appendix 2). During this forum, stakeholders from Academia (UNIPA; UÉvora, Università di Messina, Università Kore di Enna, Università di Catania), Policy Makers (Commissario per l'emergenza siccità in agricoltura della Regione Siciliana, Assessorato Energia e ai Servizi di Pubblica Utilità della Regione Siciliana, Assessorato Agricoltura, Sviluppo Rurale e Pesca mediterranea della Regione Siciliana), Foundations (Fondazione Utilitatis), Industry (SUEZ, Acciona Agua SA, AMAP Spa, FISIA ITALIMPIANTI, Marnavi Spa), EU Initiatives representatives (WestMED blue economy initiative) and Civil Society (engineers, professionals, etc.) have discussed the objectives of the project and what kind of contributions they could give to this project or other future projects, meeting the needs of regional stakeholders.

The problem of the sustainability of water supply has been identified as particularly relevant and critical, in order to satisfy demand in Sicily and the minor islands. During the RSF, the state-of-the-art desalination processes and technologies, the potential application in the regional context, the related technologies and the possible integrations in the circular economy, the aspects of environmental, social and economic sustainability, the current implementations and the future prospects were presented and critically discussed. The Forum was an opportunity for all stakeholders to meet and allowed a dialogue between experts from the world of scientific and technological research, industry, institutions and operators in the sector.

Figure 2.6.1. RSF in Palermo (April 2024)

The percentage distribution of actors in the RSF is presented in Figure 2.6.2.

Figure 2.6.2: Percentage distribution of actor types among the overall audience of the RSF in Palermo

3. WATER-ENERGY STRATEGY SYMPOSIUM

The national Water-Energy Strategy Symposium (WESSymp) was designed as an event “*aiming at the presentation and discussion of the potential role of Solar-driven water production and wastewater treatment technologies in the objectives of the National Energy and Climate Plan, as well as of the potential for industrial development and technology exports stemming from the application of the existing/developing Industrial capacity to the technological solutions sought in Sol2H2O.[...]*”.

Originally sought as a 2-day event, soon became clear that engaging 4-Helix actors for such a duration would not be easily achievable. Without compromising the objective and scope of the event, namely:

- the presentation of Sol2H2O technological solutions;
- their role in the decarbonization objectives of both the National Energy and Climate Plan and the European 2050 Energy Roadmap objectives;
- National Industrial capacities;
- alternative R&I work, competitor technological concepts, regulatory environment and targeted markets;
- Presentations by both the Sol2H2O Consortium, Policy and Industrial actors,

the event was shortened to a 1-day symposium organised on the 6th of February 2025 (M27), at the University of Évora.

Besides the national event in Évora (Portugal – see 3.1. Water-Energy Strategy Symposium) that was planned in the GA, an additional national event was also organised in Palermo (Italy – see 3.2. National Water Energy Strategy Symposium).

3.1 Water-Energy Strategy Symposium (Portugal)

Being a national symposium, the event was in Portuguese, exclusively onsite, and the presentations and discussion were not recorded, so as not to inhibit the participation.

The agenda, presented in Figure 3.1, included a visit to the research infrastructure presentations on the Sol2H2O team side, on:

- Sol2H2O project and Water-Energy Nexus;
- Sol2H2O Pilot;

- Competitiveness aspects;
- Related value chain coverage.

The agenda also included presentations from:

- Policy actors - Administration of the Alentejo Hydrographic Region (ARH Alentejo), framing Sol2H2O technological solutions in the scope of the new Urban Waste Water Directive (DARU) and the challenges for the APA/ARH Alentejo area of jurisdiction; and the Water and Waste Services Regulatory Entity, presenting the challenges of transposing the new DARU Directive and associated investments;
- Industry actors - Lisbon Water Company (EPAL), presenting their challenges in the Energy Neutrality Plan, Water and Waste Madeira company, presenting their expertise in desalination in Portugal: 45 years of desalination on the island of Porto Santo, and the Hydraulics & Water Resources Resilience Department of EDP (Energies of Portugal), presenting models for predicting inflows in the management of hydroelectric plants.

The symposium finished with a round table, with a moderated discussion with actors from the Academia (NOVA University Lisbon), Civil Society (National Federation of Irrigators of Portugal), and Industry (Litoral Central Waters), and the discussion was also opened to all the symposium participants.

06.02.2025		
09.00	Visita técnica à Infraestrutura de Investigação da UÉvora	Autocarro
12.00	Apresentação do projeto Sol2H2O e do Nexo Água-Energia	Pedro Horta Universidade de Évora
12.15	Piloto Sol2H2O, competitividade e cadeias de valor	Frederico Felizardo Universidade de Évora
12.45	Almoço	
14.00	A nova Diretiva das Águas Residuais Urbanas (DARU) e os desafios para a área de jurisdição da APA/ARH Alentejo	Ana Rodrigues Administração da Região Hidrográfica do Alentejo
14.20	Desafios da transposição da nova Diretiva DARU e investimentos associados	Vera Eiró Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos
14.40	Plano de neutralidade energética da EPAL/AdVT - Desafios	Nuno Medeiros e Rodrigo Marques EPAL - Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres
15.00	A dessalinização em Portugal: 45 anos de dessalinização na ilha do Porto Santo	Nuno Pereira Água e Resíduos da Madeira
15.20	Modelos de previsão de afluências na gestão de aproveitamentos hidroelétricos	Pedro Pinto Departamento de Hydraulics & Water Resources Resilience (EDP)
15.40	Coffee break	
16.00	Mesa-redonda Nexo Água-Energia: integração de energias renováveis na produção e tratamento de água	Manuela Morais Universidade de Évora (Moderação) João Crespo Universidade Nova de Lisboa Carina Arranja Federação Nacional de Regantes Sandra Jorge Águas do Centro Litoral Participação de todos os oradores e público presente
17.30	Fim	

Figure 3.1.1. WESSymp agenda

One of the contents raising special attention among the audience was that related to the value chain coverage, at both regional and national levels, of Sol2H2O Beyond SoA technologies, from which important conclusions could be drawn:

- at the regional level, Sol2H2O related value chains can be covered by existing companies at a scarce 19% level regarding installation activities, at 40% regarding O&M activities, and no capabilities can be found at the manufacturing activities level;
- at the national level, these values rise to 59%, at manufacturing, and 100% at both installation and O&M levels.

This study rendered clear that an engagement of industrial actors around Sol2H2O technological solutions is likely to benefit from a national scoped partnership. Following this conclusion and suggestions from the audience, the organisation of a second national took place.

An additional event will take place in Porto, in complementarity with Sol2H2O's presence at an Industrial Fair on Water and Energy in Porto, in late September.

Both announcements and news about the WESSymp were published on Sol2H2O communication channels (social media, newsletter and website, Figure 3.2), and the authorised presentations are available on Sol2H2O Zenodo and website: <https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/media-en/#presentations>.

A press release was published to announce the WESSymp and another one on the proceedings and main conclusions (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/media-en/#in-the-media>).

Figure 3.1.2. WESSymp announcement on Sol2H2O website (News section)

Table 3.1.1 summarises the number of participants and the expected level of success.

Table 3.1.1: Number of participants in WESSymp and level of success (KPI)

	Level of Success	Registrations
Water-Energy Strategy Symposium	Good: 15-25 registrations Very Good: 26-40 registrations Excellent: >40 registrations	Total: 55 External: 40

The 55 participants included: 40 external participants, being 12 from Policy, 5 from Academia, and 22 from Industry (Appendix 2). The percentage distribution of external participants, by type of actor, is presented in the graphic of Figure 3.1.3.

Figure 3.1.3: Percentage distribution of actor types among the audience of the WESSymp

The WESSymp included a visit to Herdade da Mitra, where the UÉvora Research Infrastructure is located (Figure 3.1.4).

Figure 3.1.4. WESSymp (February 2025)

After the symposium, a satisfaction survey was presented to the participants (by the end of the event, with a QR code and sent by email to allow further answers) and 9 answers were received (Appendix 3), revealing that 55,6% of the participants who answered the survey were satisfied and 44,4% totally satisfied with the symposium (Figure 3.1.5), and that the WESSymp corresponded to their expectations (Figure 3.1.6). To the question “Do you see an opportunity in the technological solutions presented? If so, to what extent?”, participants answered:

- *“Harnessing solar energy”;*
- *“Yes, optimising water and energy systems without dissociating one from the other.”;*
- *“Yes, mining brine from desalination plants can be an opportunity”;*
- *“Yes, use of desalinated water”;*
- *“Yes, but with the inherent difficulties of introducing systems that aren't mastered by the big industries.”;*
- *“Since we will never have a technology with zero environmental impact, I believe it is of the utmost importance to exploit the natural resources we have, and the combination of solar energy and desalination comes as a contribution to meeting a human need. In fact,*

as a great thinker would say, ‘One small step for man, one giant leap for mankind’, and another great sage who states that the principle of wisdom is: acquire it, and use everything you have to acquire understanding. This is to say that there are no small discoveries, but great beginnings. And yes, I think we are facing the beginning of a new cycle of intrusion, development and expansion of what the human mind is capable of developing. I realise that I’m not making much of a contribution in academic terms, but for that, I know you’re doing your best and you’ll do great things in that direction.”;

- “Yes, the desalination plant solution is a solution for the future.”;
- “A huge opportunity”;
- “Environmental sustainability”.

Numa escala de 1 a 5, como classifica a sua satisfação geral com o Water-Energy Strategy Symposium?

9 respostas

Figure 3.1.5. WESSymp Satisfaction survey (On a scale of 1 - totally unsatisfied to 5 - totally satisfied, how would you rate your overall satisfaction with the Water-Energy Strategy Symposium?)

O Water-Energy Strategy Symposium correspondeu às suas expetativas?

9 respostas

Figure 3.1.6. WESSymp Satisfaction survey (Did the Water-Energy Strategy Symposium live up to your expectations?, where blue means “yes” and red means “no”)

3.2. National Water Energy Strategy Symposium (Italy)

The National Water-Energy Strategy Symposium was a 2-day National Symposium covering Seawater Desalination and Related Technologies in the context of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus – with invited speakers from Policy, Industry and Civil Society actors. The Symposium was organized by UNIPA and took place at the University of Palermo (Figure 3.2.1) on the 1st and 2nd of July 2025, with the attendance of 79 participants (the attendance list is provided in Appendix 2).

Table 3.2.1 summarises the number of participants and the expected level of success.

Table 3.2.1: Number of participants in WESSymp and level of success (KPI)

	Level of Success	Registrations
Water-Energy Strategy Symposium	Good: 15-25 registrations Very Good: 26-40 registrations Excellent: >40 registrations	Total: 79 External: 73

The sustainability of water supply has become increasingly critical in several regions of Italy. In this context, the use of unconventional sources—such as sustainable seawater desalination—can play a key role in mitigating water scarcity. It also supports an integrated and circular approach to water resource management, enhancing the resilience of supply systems.

Being a national symposium, the event was in Italian, exclusively onsite, and the presentations and discussion were not recorded, so as not to inhibit the participation.

Figure 3.2.1. WESSymp at UNIPA (July 2025)

The agenda, presented in Figure 3.2.2, included presentations on the Sol2H2O team's side on circular and sustainable desalination processes. The agenda also included:

- Interventions from authorities:

- Policy actors, such as the National Extraordinary Commissioner for the adoption of urgent interventions related to water scarcity (Presidency of the Council of Ministers of Italy);
- Councillor for Agriculture, Rural Development and Mediterranean Fisheries of Sicily;
- General Manager Civil Protection Department of Sicily;
- Basin Authority of the Hydrographic District of Sicily;
- Department of Water and Waste, Department of Energy and Public Utilities of Sicily.
- Interventions from water service management companies (AMAP, Acquedotto Pugliese, SICILIACQUE) on water resources management.
- Presentations from Academic actors on:
 - the drought in Sicily, water emergency and climate adaptation strategies;
 - Italian and European legislation on seawater desalination.
- Interventions from Civil Society actors, such as the Italian Association for Desalination and Water Reuse (AIDARA) and from WestMED, presenting the WestMED initiative in Italy and the opportunity to create an Italian supply chain in the desalination field market;
- Presentations from Industry actors, with six different General Contractors and Technology Suppliers (FISIA Italimpianti, Suez Italia, Acciona Agua, Schneider, Danfoss, ResourSEAs) presenting their products and/or services in Sol2H2O related fields.

Programma

Martedì 1 Luglio 2025 ore 14:00-19:00

14:00 Registrazione dei partecipanti

14:30 Apertura dei lavori e moderazione

Dr Silvio Oliva, Presidente AIDARA - Prof. Giorgio Micale, Università di Palermo

14:45-16:00 Interventi:

Prof. Ing. Vincenzo di Dio, Presidente Ordine degli Ingegneri Provincia di Palermo

Prof. Ing. Livan Fratini Direttore Dipartimento di Ingegneria Università di Palermo

Prof. Ing. Maurizio Cellura Direttore CSTE - Centro di Sostenibilità e Transizione Ecologica di Ateneo

Dott. Nicola Dell'Acqua, Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri, Commissario straordinario nazionale per l'adozione di interventi urgenti connessi al fenomeno della scarsità idrica

Prof. Ing. Salvatore Barbagallo, Assessore all'Agricoltura, dello Sviluppo Rurale e della Pesca mediterranea della Regione Siciliana

Dott. Francesco Colianni, Assessore regionale all'Energia e ai servizi di pubblica utilità, della Regione Siciliana

Ing. Salvo Cocina, Dirigente Generale Dipartimento Protezione Civile – Sicilia

Ing. Leonardo Santoro, Segretario Generale Autorità di Bacino del Distretto Idrografico della Sicilia

Ing. Mario Cassarà, Dipartimento dell'Acqua e dei Rifiuti, Assessorato dell'Energia e dei Servizi di Pubblica Utilità della Regione Siciliana

16:00-16:15

Ing. They Alkahtani, General Manager of Strategic Partnerships, Saudi Water Authority – Secretary General, Global Prize for Innovation in Water, "Empowering Innovation for Water Sustainability: The Global Role of the Saudi Water Authority"

16:15 - 19:00 La gestione delle risorse idriche situazione corrente e prospettive future

Prof. Leonardo Noto, Università di Palermo, "Siccità in Sicilia 2023-2025: tra emergenza idrica e strategie di adattamento climatico"

Ing. Giovanni Sciortino, Amministratore Unico AMAP, "Il ruolo della dissalazione delle acque nella gestione del servizio idrico integrato: aspetti economici, sociali ed ambientali"

Ing. Gaetano Barbone, Direzione Ingegneria, Acquedotto Pugliese, "L'approccio sostenibile di Acquedotto Pugliese alla dissalazione. Una sfida per il soddisfacimento del fabbisogno idrico e la salvaguardia degli ecosistemi regionali tra acqua salmastra e acqua di mare"

Ing. Massimo Burruano, Direttore operativo SICILIACQUE, "Emergenza idrica e dissalazione in Sicilia: il punto di vista del gestore sovrabito nel breve e nel lungo periodo"

Prof. Ing. Andrea Cipollina, Prof. Ing. Giorgio Micale, Università di Palermo, "Processi di dissalazione circolari e sostenibili: l'esperienza dei progetti di ricerca dell'Università di Palermo"

Dr.ssa Marta Nigrelli, Università di Palermo, "Dissalazione delle acque di mare: legislazione italiana ed europea"

Ing. Alessandro Viviani, The European House Ambrosetti, "Global Prize for Innovation in Water - Celebrating Breakthroughs Shaping the Future of Water"

19:00 Chiusura dei lavori della prima giornata

Programma
Mercoledì 2 Luglio 2025 ore 9:00 - 13:30

09:00 Registrazione dei partecipanti

09:15 - 09:45

Saluto di apertura dei lavori: Dr Silvio Oliva, Presidente AIDARA

Dr.ssa Benedetta Brioschi, The European House Ambrosetti, "Il Libro Bianco Valore Acqua per l'Italia e il contributo della dissalazione alla soluzione della scarsità idrica in Italia"

09:45 - 12:45 Interventi dei General Contractors e Fornitori di Tecnologia

Moderazione: Dr.ssa Benedetta Brioschi, The European House Ambrosetti

Ing. Giorgio Prato Florito, FISIA Italimpianti, "Effluenti a mare degli impianti di dissalazione ad osmosi inversa e relativa legislazione vigente in Italia"

Ing. Laura Cammili, Suez Italia - "L'integrazione della dissalazione nella gestione complessiva della risorsa idrica: un approccio a 360°"

Ing. Giulio Ricciuto, Direttore OSM Acciona Agua, "Impianti modulari containerizzati. Esperienze a confronto"

Dr Stefano Frega, Danfoss, "Massimizzare l'efficienza dei sistemi a Osmosi Inversa"

Donato Pasquale, Schneider Electric, "Automazione avanzata negli impianti di dissalazione di ultima generazione"

Ing. Fabrizio Vicari, Resourseas, "Verso un'industria unificata per l'estrazione di sostanze chimiche, minerali e acqua dall'acqua di mare"

12:45 L'Iniziativa WestMED in Italia e l'opportunità di creare una filiera italiana nel settore della dissalazione - WestMED Assistance Mechanism, National Hub Italy

13:00 Dibattito

13:30 Chiusura dei lavori

Figure 3.2.2. National WESSymp agenda

Announcements about the National WESSymp were published online on the UNIPA website (<https://www.unipa.it/La-dissalazione-dellacqua-di-mare-e-le-tecnologie-correlate-nel-contesto-del-Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem-WEFE-Nexus/>) (Figure 3.2.3).

The screenshot shows the website of the University of Palermo (UNIPA). At the top, there is the university logo and name, along with navigation links for languages (ENG, ZHO, GER, SPA) and social media (X, f, @, in). Below this is a blue navigation bar with links for 'SEGRETERIE STUDENTI', 'DIPARTIMENTI', 'SCUOLA DI MEDICINA E CHIRURGIA', 'POLI TERRITORIALI', and 'BIBLIOTECHE E ARCHIVIO STORICO'. The main content area features a headline: 'La dissalazione dell'acqua di mare e le tecnologie correlate nel contesto del Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus'. Below the headline, it states the date '1-lug-2025' and includes a 'Ascolta' icon. The text describes the event: 'Martedì 1° luglio, alle 14.00, nell'Aula Capità del Dipartimento di Ingegneria (Ed. 7, Campus universitario di Viale delle Scienze), si tiene l'incontro di apertura del primo simposio nazionale sulla dissalazione.' It further details the initiative, organized by UNIPA, AIDARA, and the provincial engineering order, with participation from regional and national stakeholders. A key message is highlighted: 'In programma approfondimenti sui processi e le tecnologie di dissalazione, sul potenziale applicativo in ambito regionale e nazionale, sulle implementazioni correnti e le prospettive future, sulle tecnologie correlate e le possibili integrazioni in ambito di economia circolare, e sugli aspetti di sostenibilità ambientale, sociale ed economica nel contesto del Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus.' The announcement concludes with 'I lavori proseguono mercoledì 2 luglio.' At the bottom, there is a 'Visualizza il programma' link, a 'Parole Chiave:' section with the text 'articolo notizia unica dissalazione ingegneria', and social media sharing icons for Google+, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter.

Figure 3.2.3. WESSymp announcement on UNIPA website (Home section)

The Symposium presented and critically examined the state-of-the-art in desalination processes and technologies, their potential applications at both regional and national levels, current implementations, and future prospects. Related technologies and possible integrations within the framework of the circular economy were also explored, along with environmental, social, and economic sustainability considerations in the context of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus.

The Symposium offered a valuable opportunity for all stakeholders to engage in dialogue. It brought together experts from scientific and technological research, industry, institutions, and professionals in the sector to exchange ideas and promote collaboration. The percentage distribution of actors in the WESSymp is presented in Figure 3.2.4.

Figure 3.2.4. Percentage distribution of actor types among the overall audience of the WESSymp in Palermo

4. WATER-ENERGY TRANSITION SYMPOSIUM

The Water-Energy Transition Symposium (WETSymp) was a 2-day International Symposium that aimed to present and discuss the potential role of solar water production and treatment technologies and Water-Energy technologies in the objectives of the National Energy and Climate Plan, as well as the potential for industrial development and technology exports resulting from the application of existing/developing industrial capacity to the technological solutions sought in Sol2H2O.

This international symposium took place in two stages: a discussion at a national level in each of the consortium's member countries (Portugal, Italy and Spain) with a selected group of key players in this field, and a discussion at an international level to compare the results of the different talks.

After project meeting #5 in which the dates for WETSymp were pre-defined, the consortium partners, in online meetings, defined the methodology (with the support of Leonel Alegre, from UÉvora), the dates and the questions to be asked of the participants on each national day, so that they would be the same on the country days and comparable.

Based on the 6-3-5 methodology, in which 6 participants write down 3 ideas within 5 minutes, in order to encourage a greater number of ideas, which can then be selected and discussed, it was decided to subscribe to the Miro online platform (or Mentimeter platform) to be used in the sessions in the three countries. This platform allows participants to simultaneously write down ideas, simulating writing on sticky notes, without seeing what the others are writing, in the first phase, so that ideas are not influenced. Subsequently, the ideas were revealed and grouped, with the support of the participants, if they were repeated or similar, and a vote was taken on them, so that the 3 most important ideas were defined in response to each of the questions presented (Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1. Example of idea voting on the Portuguese day, using Miro

These Portuguese and Italian WETSymp events have taken place online, to allow the participation of relevant stakeholders who had already been present in Évora recently, in the case of the Portuguese Day, coming from different places in the country, and also because the final day will include participants from different countries. The Spanish Day took place onsite, as a preliminary event to the upcoming “XIV Congreso Internacional de AEDyR”, and was jointly organised by ITC and CIEMAT, as both Sol2H2O partners are from Spain.

The presentations and discussions were not recorded, so as not to inhibit the participation.

For the Portuguese, Italian and Spanish days, a small group of relevant stakeholders was invited, representing the 4Helix level of Academia, Policy makers, Industry and Civil Society.

The Portuguese, Italian and Spanish Day, both the online and onsite events, followed the same agenda:

- 1 hour - Introduction, participants' presentations and Sol2H2O project presentation
- 2 hours + break - Idea production (5 questions, 3 ideas/question); idea clustering; idea classification (each participant has 3 votes to classify the 3 “best” ideas for each question)
- 30 minutes - Final discussion

The questions defined by the partners were:

1. What kind of barriers to wastewater treatment and reuse for irrigation might be found by water management or water technology development companies?
2. How can we overcome these barriers?
3. What kind of challenges should be overcome for a real market implementation of ZLD solutions?
4. What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side?
5. How could water storage be a solution for energy storage strategies in the case of large-scale renewable energy systems?

Invitations were sent to the selected participants by each consortium partner. The first day to be organised was the Portuguese day after a Doodle was sent to the participants to select the best schedule. A Zoom link was sent for a session of around 4 hours, as defined agenda. The Italian day was organised in a similar way, the Spanish day was organised along the “XIV Congreso Internacional de AEDyR”, and for the International Day, the scheduling was defined by the consortium before sending the invitations.

The agenda, the questions and the presentations were translated into each partner language in the case of Portugal, Spain and Italy.

Taking advantage of the EDS (European Desalination Society) 2025 conference organised in Portugal (Oporto), an on-site parallel session to present Sol2H2O and the results obtained on the online Portuguese day. The results produced are presented below.

Announcements about the WETSymp international day were published on Sol2H2O communication channels (social media, newsletter and website), besides the invitations sent by

email. News about the national days and the international day were also published in Sol2H2O communication channels (Figure 4.2), and the authorised presentations are available on Sol2H2O Zenodo and website: <https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/media-en/#presentations>.

International symposium discusses water-energy transition

11/07/2025

The event brought together experts, policymakers, researchers and industry representatives to discuss water-energy transition

Figure 4.2. News about the WETSymp international day on the Sol2H2O website

The national day events in each country stood for a voting audience as illustrated in Figure 4.3.

WETSymp national days voting participants

Figure 4.3. Voting participants, by country and by sector

4.1 Portuguese Day

The Portuguese Day was held online, on the 22nd of April 2025, in Portuguese, with 16 participants, of whom 9 were voting participants (Table 4.1.1 and Figure 4.1.1).

Table 4.1.1: Portuguese Day participants list

Name	Institution	Sector	Voting participant
Dominique Livriero	UÉvora (organisation/Sol2H2O team)	-	•
Frederico Felizardo	UÉvora (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	•
Maria Helena Novais	UÉvora (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	•
Leonel Alegre	UÉvora (organisation)	-	•
Pedro Horta	UÉvora (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	•
Guillermo Zaragoza	CIEMAT (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	•
Juan Antonio Bencomo	ITC (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	•
Anabela Rebelo	APA - Portuguese Environment Agency	Policy Maker	•
Carina Arranja	FENAREG - National Federation of Irrigators of Portugal	Civil Society	•
Diana Cordeiro	FENAREG - National Federation of Irrigators of Portugal	Civil Society	•
Daniela Pereira	Aqualia	Industry	•
Tiago Parente	Aquapor	Industry	•
Rui Sequeira	ARH Alentejo - Administration of the Alentejo Hydrographic Region	Policy Maker	•
Sara Correia	ZERO - Sustainable Earth System Association	Civil Society	•
Sandra Jorge	AdP - Waters of Portugal	Industry	•
Nuno Pereira	Aguas e Resíduos da Madeira	Industry	•

Figure 4.1.1. WETSymp Portuguese Day

The meeting started with a presentation of the Sol2H2O project, focusing on its objectives and impacts, clarifying the technological concept, competitiveness, TRL levels and value chain.

Each question was presented to the voting participants, and each participant could answer with two ideas to each question, using the “stick notes” on Miro, without seeing the ideas from the

other participants. After 5 minutes, all ideas were shown, and a clustering of them was done collectively, as some ideas were the same or similar (Figure 4.1.2).

The defined clusters to be voted on were highlighted with a different colour (Figure 4.1.2), and each participant could vote for the three ideas they found most important (Figure 4.1.3). In the event of a tie, a second vote was taken, with only one vote per participant on the tied ideas.

Figure 4.1.2. Clustering of ideas answered in question 1

Figure 4.1.3. The three most voted ideas answered in question 1

Tables 4.1.2. to 4.1.6 summarise the results of the session (results from Miro in Appendix 6).

Table 4.1.2: Answers to question 1.

Question 1	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What kind of barriers to wastewater treatment and reuse for irrigation might be found by water management or water technology development companies?	Social challenges: public acceptance, both from farmers and consumers	1
	Cost of the technology	2
	Transport of treated water to the point of use	3
	Technical challenges, namely in the management of emerging pollutants	—
	Removal of micropollutants: cost support	—
	Legislative issues	—
	Storage	—
	Water price for farmers	—

Table 4.1.3: Answers to question 2.

Question 2	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
How can we overcome these barriers: social challenges?	Communication and transparency	1
	Frequent analytical monitoring	—
How can we overcome these barriers: cost of technology?	Speed in the bureaucratic process	—
	Research for the development of new technologies	3
	Taking advantage of economies of scale	—
	Technology with nature-based solutions	—
	Possible subsidisation	—
How can we overcome these barriers: transport of treated water?	Territorial management	2
	Dedicated transport system for reused water	—

Table 4.1.4: Answers to question 3.

Question 3	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What kind of challenges should be overcome for a real market implementation of ZLD solutions?	Economic feasibility of the project at a large scale	1
	Reuse of final brine – Potassium, Boron, Sodium chloride	2
	Final destination of the brine – area required for evaporation at real scale	3
	Debureaucratisation of the licensing system	—
	Upscaling of treatment solutions (from research to practice)	—

Table 4.1.5: Answers to question 4.

Question 4	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side: economic feasibility?	Encouragement of industrial consortia	—
	Association of potential users; economies of scale	—
	Market study for products extracted from brine	3
What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side: reuse of final brine?	Research on ZLD solutions to identify potential applications of products for industrial or commercial use (e.g. detergents)	1
	Partnerships with companies/sectors that could use the products derived from brine	—
	Integration of water production with solutions for brine utilisation	—
What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side: final destination of the brine?	Creation of clear standards for the final destination of brine	—
	Research into rapid evaporation/heat concentration solutions	2

Table 4.1.6: Answers to question 5.

Question 5	Categories of answers	
How could water storage be a solution for energy storage strategies in the case of large-scale renewable energy systems?	Promotion of reversible storage systems	1
	Geo-strategic storage locations for energy purposes	2

A parallel session in the European Desalination Society (EDS) Conference 2025 was also organised as an extension of the Portuguese Day of the WETSymp, with 12 participants (Table 4.1.7 and Figure 4.1.4).

Table 4.1.7: Parallel session in EDS Conference participants list

Name	Institution	Sector
Frederico Felizardo	UÉvora (Sol2H2O team)	Academy
Maria Helena Novais	UÉvora (Sol2H2O team)	Academy
Pedro Horta	UÉvora (Sol2H2O team)	Academy
Luís Alves	Seamoretech	Industry
Maria Norberta de Pinho	Instituto Superior Técnico	Academy
João Crespo	Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica, NOVA University	Academy
Behzad Sichani	INEGI, FEUP (Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto)	Academy
André Torres Pinto	ALICE, FEUP (Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto)	Academy
António Ferreira	ALICE, FEUP (Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto)	Academy
Raquel Freitas	Águas do Algarve	Industry
Carlos Gonçalves	CG Aqua Solutions	Industry
Noémia Santos	Águas do Douro e Paiva	Industry

Figure 4.1.4. Sol2H2O parallel session, in the EDS conference

This session began with a brief presentation of the Sol2H2O project, focusing on the infrastructure installed at the University of Évora – a pilot for water production through solar desalination and "Zero-Liquid Discharge" solutions, as well as associated value chains.

During this presentation, the five issues discussed in the preliminary online event were presented, with only questions 1 and 5 raising comments by the participants:

1. **Wastewater Treatment – Challenges:** What challenges might water management or technology development companies face in wastewater treatment and reuse (e.g., for irrigation)?
Importance of adapting water from different Alternative Sources for the production of various agricultural crops. This includes conducting tests to evaluate the quality of treated wastewater for irrigation, based on the intended crop and levels of requirements (e.g., the ability to perform disinfection tests, including ARB and ARGs, at the University of Évora facilities).
2. **Wastewater Treatment – Solutions:** How can we overcome the challenges mentioned above?
Communication was highlighted as one of the key solutions presented and discussed by participants.
3. **ZLD (Zero Liquid Discharge) – Challenges:** What challenges must be overcome to successfully implement ZLD solutions in the market?
4. **ZLD – Solutions:** What technological, economic, regulatory, environmental, or social solutions do you propose to overcome the challenges associated with ZLD?
5. **Water Storage:** How can water storage be a solution for energy storage in large-scale renewable energy systems?

The discussion focused on the creation of an Association for Desalination and Wastewater Reuse – Alternative Water Resources. There was clear interest from those present, with the suggestion that it should initially start as a cluster of ideas that could be formalised later. For this, an Agenda should be created, outlining the mission, objectives, and activity schedule. It was mentioned that the initial focus of this group could be *Water for Reuse (ApR)*, given the new legislative requirements (implementation of the new Urban Wastewater Directive). Therefore, it is important to include the operators of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in Portugal and to identify which WWTPs will implement tertiary water treatment processes. Representatives from private companies expressed interest in this cluster/association, especially in networking activities, due to the difficulty of establishing collaborations in Portugal and distributing products within the country. The importance of creating a list/database of companies and institutions active in these topics was emphasised, as it would facilitate, for example, the creation of consortia for preparing funding applications.

Therefore, it was agreed that:

1. **The University of Évora** will begin compiling a database of entities related to these topics, including:
 - Entities from the scientific and technological system;
 - Regulatory bodies;
 - Public companies;
 - Companies from polluting sectors (e.g., cork industries, dairies);
 - Operators of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs).
2. This database may also be supplemented by a survey of companies/individuals using Treated Wastewater, including its use by the wastewater producer itself.
3. The organisation of a meeting in Évora to continue this discussion.
4. The University of Évora will prepare a draft of an Agenda for this association/cluster.

4.2. Italian Day

The Italian Day was held online, on the 30th of June 2025, in Italian, with 9 participants, of whom 6 were voting participants (Table 4.2.1), and following the same procedure as described in 4.1.

Table 4.2.1: Italian Day participants list

Name	Institution	Sector	Voting participant
Nunzio Cancilla	UNIPA (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	•
Andrea Cipollina	UNIPA (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	•
Leonel Alegre	UÉvora (organisation)	-	•
Fabrizio Vicari	ResourSEAs	Industry	•
Giulio D'Arpa	MARE MAG	Industry	•
Antonella Filingeri	ResourSEAs	Industry	•
Fabio Pupillo	SOPES	Industry	•
Angelo Catania	SELIS	Industry	•
Silvio Oliva	AIDARA	Civil Society	•

Tables 4.2.2. to 4.2.6 summarise the results of the session (results from Miro in Appendix 7).

Table 4.2.2: Answers to question 1.

Question 1	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What kind of barriers to wastewater treatment and reuse for irrigation might be found by water management or water technology development companies?	Physical distance between the treated water and the required water	—
	Cost of treated water vs. willingness to pay by end user	2
	Regulations sometimes conflicting	3
	Public opinion against the use of wastewater	1

Table 4.2.3: Answers to question 2.

Question 2	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
How can we overcome these barriers: public opinion?	Campaigns explaining how treated water is safe	1
How can we overcome these barriers: cost of treated water?	Economic incentives for the use of treated water	2
	Distribute the water cost over all the water used, regardless of the origin	—
	Sector agreements for treated water use	—
How can we overcome these barriers: regulations?	Structural revision of the laws (towards simplification)	3
	Water reuse, yes, but who is willing to authorise it, needs clearer regulatory frameworks	—

Table 4.2.4: Answers to question 3.

Question 3	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What kind of challenges should be overcome for a real market implementation of ZLD solutions?	Membrane processes are currently unable to process brines	–
	Investment in innovation	–
	Using a lot of energy, often from non-renewable sources, would sometimes be unsustainable	1
	The problem of solid waste disposal	–
	Obtain products and specifics with a purity that meets the market	2
	Better information	–
	Making the brine valorisation process economically competitive	3
	Non-standardised processes (ISO, etc.)	–
	Accessing established markets with new technologies	–

Table 4.2.5: Answers to question 4.

Question 4	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side: using a lot of energy?	Use of renewable energy	–
	In tenders, favour projects where integration with RES is greatest.	–
What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side: purity that meets the market?	Virtual markets for matching supply and demand	2
	Recovery and production of salts and metals with established markets	–
What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side: brine valorisation process economically competitive?	Legislative constraints requiring the valorisation of at least a portion of the produced brine	3
	Rewards for projects that include ZLD solutions	1
	More investment in innovation	–

Table 4.2.6: Answers to question 5.

Question 5	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
How could water storage be a solution for energy storage strategies in the case of large-scale renewable energy systems?	It can be a good solution in cases where this is possible	3
	Conversion to potential energy, electricity can be used for pumping water in high reservoirs	2
	Increasing production during peak hours of renewable energy availability	1
	The discharge of brine from desalination plants could generate energy via a turbine	–

4.3. Spanish Day

The Spanish Day was held onsite, on the 23rd of June 2025, in Spanish, with 27 participants, of whom 22 were voting participants (Table 4.3.1 and Figure 4.3.1). The meeting started with a presentation of the Sol2H2O project and the WE nexus, focusing on its objectives, impacts and clarifying the technological concept. Four presentations were given by the invited speakers: *“Challenges of carbon neutrality within the new urban wastewater treatment and reuse directives”*, *“Decarbonization plan for the public irrigation water supply service on the island of Tenerife”*, *“Barriers and opportunities in the pursuit of energy efficiency in desalinated water production and industrial wastewater treatment”* and *“Success Story: 100% Renewable El Hierro (Reversible Hydro-Wind Power Plant)”*. After a coffee break, the two Living Labs coordinated by Sol2H2O project partners were presented *“Incorporating solar energy and the circular economy into desalination - roadmap for Spanish living labs: DESAL+ LIVING LAB and SUSTAINABLE DESALINATION LIVING LAB”*.

Finally, the plenary debate took place, entitled *“Challenges and Barriers of the Water-Energy Nexus: Roadmap to Achieving a Sustainable Water-Energy Nexus in Water Production and Treatment”*. The Mentimeter app was used to develop the debate, allowing attendees to respond and vote on the various questions posed using their mobile devices. A participatory debate followed on-site after each question.

Each question was presented to the voting participants, and each participant could answer with two ideas to each question, using the Mentimeter app, without seeing the ideas from the other participants. After 5 minutes, all ideas were shown, and a clustering of them was done collectively, as some ideas were the same or similar (Figure 4.3.2).

Table 4.3.1: Spanish Day participants list

Name	Institution	Sector	Voting participant
	CIEMAT (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	●
	CIEMAT (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	●
	ITC (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	●
	ITC (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	●
	ITC (Sol2H2O team)	Academy	●
	TAGUA	Industry	●
	TAGUA	Industry	●

Name	Institution	Sector	Voting participant
	TAGUA	Industry	•
	Gorona del Viento	Policy	•
	Gorona del Viento	Policy	•
	Grupo EVM	Industry	•
	ITC	Industry	•
	Asociación para la Investigación de la Macaronesia	Policy	•
	WEG	Industry	•
	Gobierno de Canarias	Policy	•
	BALTEN	Industry	•
	BALTEN	Industry	•
	DANFOSS	Industry	•
	Ecoagua Ingenieros SL	Industry	•
	Ayuntamiento de San Miguel de Abona	Policy	•
	Consejo Insular de Aguas de Tenerife	Policy	•
	Consejo Insular de Aguas de Tenerife	Policy	•
	Consejo Insular de Aguas de Tenerife	Policy	•
	Consejo Insular de Aguas de Tenerife	Policy	•
	Universidad de Alicante	Academy	•
	University of Seville	Academy	•
	Global Omnium	Industry	•

Figure 4.3.1. WETSymp Spanish Day

Tables 4.3.2. to 4.3.6 summarise the results of the session (results from Mentimeter in Appendix 8).

Table 4.3.2: Answers to question 1.

Question 1	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What kind of barriers to wastewater treatment and reuse for irrigation might be found by water management or water technology development companies?	Administrative and regulatory barriers	1
	Analytical controls requested do not discriminate between the size of the systems	2
	Social perception of the water quality by users	3

Table 4.3.3: Answers to question 2.

Question 2	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
How can we overcome these barriers?	Greater social communication, training and awareness	1
	Improving the regulatory framework, involving all stakeholders	2
	Different plans for large and small systems, adapting analytical controls to the reused flow	3

Table 4.3.4: Answers to question 3.

Question 3	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What kind of challenges should be overcome for a real market implementation of ZLD solutions?	Highly expensive process (energy and investments)	1
	Energy cost and profit of derived products	2
	There is no census of industrial waste for the purpose of valorisation, awareness of usefulness/need	3

Table 4.3.5: Answers to question 4.

Question 4	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side?	The ZLD doesn't have to be a target in every case. Each one needs to be analysed individually	1
	Greater effort in R&D&I	2
	Encourage the circular economy, seek commercial interest in recovered products	3

Table 4.3.6: Answers to question 5.

Question 5	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
How could water storage be a solution for energy storage strategies in the case of	Adapting desalination to the availability of renewable energy	1

large-scale renewable energy systems?	Reversible pumping	2
	Water management, production, transportation and distribution should be used as elements of electric power demand management	3

4.4. International Day

The International Day was held online, on the 11th of July 2025, in English, with 48 participants (Figures 4.4.1 and 4.4.2), of whom 34 were external to the Sol2H2O team, being 21 from the Industry, 4 from the Policy and 7 from the Academia/R&D institutions (2 participants could not be identified in a category; Appendix 2). Table 4.4.1 summarises the number of participants and the expected level of success.

Table 4.4.1: Number of participants in WETSymp and level of success (KPI)

	Level of Success	Registrations
Water-Energy Transition Symposium	Good: 25-50 registrations Very Good: 51-75 registrations Excellent: >75 registrations	Total: 48 External: 34

The percentage distribution of external participants, by type of actor, is presented in the graphic of Figure 4.4.1.

Figure 4.4.1: Percentage distribution of actor types among the audience of the WETSymp

Figure 4.4.2. WETSymp International Day

The meeting started with the presentation of the Sol2H2O project, focusing on its objectives and impacts, clarifying the technological concept, competitiveness, TRL levels and value chain.

A brief review of how the Portuguese, Italian and Spanish days were held was presented, comparing the participants per sector, as shown in Figure 4.3. The most voted answers to each question, in each country day, were compared (Figures 4.4.3 to 4.4.8). After this, some companies presented their work in the field of Sol2H2O technologies, with speakers from SELIS, ResourSEAS, Seamoretech, TAGUA, BALTEN, Global Omnium, Suez Italia, Maremag, and SOPES, and a final discussion, resulting in relevant conclusions, was held.

International Water Energy Symposium, 10.07.2025

1. What kind of barriers to wastewater treatment and reuse for irrigation might be found by water management or water technology development companies?

Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Social challenges: public acceptance by both farmers and consumers <i>(Desafios sociais: aceitação pública, tanto por parte dos agricultores quanto por parte dos consumidores)</i>	Cost of technology <i>(Custo da tecnologia)</i>	Transport of treated water to final use <i>(Transporte da água tratada para o uso final)</i>
Spain	Administrative and regulatory barriers <i>(Barreras administrativas y de marco regulatorio)</i>	Analytical controls requested do not discriminate between the size of the systems <i>(Los controles analíticos exigidos no tienen en cuenta el tamaño del sistema)</i>	Social perception of the water quality by users <i>(Percepción social de la calidad del recurso por parte del usuario final)</i>
Italy	Public opinion against the use of wastewater <i>(Opinione pubblica contro l'uso di acque reflue)</i>	Cost of treated water vs. willingness to pay by end user	Regulations sometimes conflicting

Figure 4.4.4. WETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 1

2. How can we overcome these barriers?

Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Communication and transparency <i>(Comunicação e transparência)</i>	Territorial management <i>(Gestão territorial)</i>	Research to develop new technologies <i>(Investigação para desenvolvimento de novas tecnologias)</i>
Spain	Greater social communication, training and awareness <i>(Mayor comunicación social, formación y concienciación)</i>	Improving the regulatory framework, involving all stakeholders <i>(Mejorando el marco normativo, Implicación de todos los agentes. Facilitar la tramitación y dotar de recursos a las administraciones)</i>	Different plans for large and small systems, adapting analytical controls to the reused flow <i>(Planes diferentes para los grandes y pequeños sistemas, adaptar los controles analíticos al caudal reutilizado)</i>
Italy	Campaigns explaining how treated water is safe <i>(Campagne informative che spieghino come l'acqua trattata sia sicura specialmente anche in contesti di scarsa disponibilità idrica)</i>	Economic incentives on the use of treated water <i>(Incentivi economici sull'utilizzo dell'acqua trattata)</i>	Structural revision of the laws (towards simplification)

Figure 4.4.5. WETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 2

3. What kind of challenges should be overcome for a real market implementation of ZLD solutions?

Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Economic viability of the project on a large scale <i>(Viabilidade económica do projeto em larga escala)</i>	Reuse of the final brine, K, B, NaCl <i>(Reaproveitamento da salmoura final, potássio, boro, cloreto de sódio)</i>	Final destination of the brine - area needed for full-scale evaporation <i>(Destino final da salmoura - área necessária para a evaporação à escala real)</i>
Spain	Highly expensive process (energy and investments) <i>(Proceso altamente costoso (energía e inversiones))</i>	Energy cost and profit of derived products <i>(Coste energético y beneficio de los productos derivados)</i>	There is no census of industrial waste for the purpose of valorization, awareness of usefulness/need <i>(No hay censo de vertidos industriales con el fin de valorizar, Concienciación de utilidad/necesidad)</i>
Italy	Using a lot of energy, often from non-renewable sources, would sometimes be unsustainable <i>(Utilizzo di parecchia energia spesso da fonti non rinnovabili, risulterebbe a volte poco sostenibile)</i>	Obtain products and specifics with a purity that meet the market	Making the brine valorization process economic competitive

Figure 4.4.6. WETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 3

International Water Energy Symposium, 10.07.2025		4. What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulation, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side?	
Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Integrate ZLD solutions research with products research to identify possible uses (Integrar a inv. das ZLD solutions com a inv. de produtos (usos industriais ou comerciais, ex. detergência) para identificar possíveis usos)	Research fast evaporation/heat concentration solutions (Investigar soluções de evaporação rápida/concentração de calor)	Market research for brine products (Estudo de mercado para os produtos retirados da salmoura)
Spain	The ZLD doesn't have to be a target in every case. Each one needs to be analyzed individually (El ZLD no tiene porque ser un objetivo en todos los casos. Hay que analizarlos uno por uno)	Greater effort in R&D&I (Mayor esfuerzo en I+D+i)	Encourage the circular economy, seek commercial interest in recovered products (Incentivar economía circular, identificar y buscar salida comercial a los productos recuperados)
Italy	Rewards for projects that include ZLD solutions (Premialità per progetti che includono soluzioni ZLD)	Virtual markets for matching supply and demand (Creare dei mercati virtuali di incontro tra domanda e offerta)	Legislative constraints requiring the valorization of at least a portion of the produced brine (Imporre vincoli legislativi che obbligano alla valorizzazione di almeno un'aliquota della salamoia prodotta)

Figure 4.4.7. WETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 4

International Water Energy Symposium, 10.07.2025		5. How could water storage be a solution for energy storage strategies in the case of large-scale renewable energy systems?	
Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Promotion of reversible storage systems (Promoção de sistemas de armazenamento reversíveis)	Geostrategic storage sites for energy purposes (Locais de armazenamento geo-estratégicos para fins energéticos)	
Spain	Adapting desalination to the availability of renewable energy (Adaptando la desalación a la disponibilidad de energía renovable)	Reversible pumping (Bombeo reversible. Se bombea agua con el excedente de energía renovable, se almacena en embalses a gran altitud y luego se turbinan para la producción de energía y el consumo local)	Water management, production, transportation and distribution should be used as elements of electric power demand management (La gestión del agua, producción, transporte y distribución, deben usarse como elementos de gestión de la demanda de energía eléctrica)
Italy	Increasing production during peak hours of renewable energy availability (Incrementare la produzione durante le ore di picco di disponibilità di energia rinnovabile)	Conversion to potential energy, electricity can be used for pumping water in high reservoirs (Conversione in energia potenziale, l'energia elettrica può essere utilizzata per il pompaggio dell'acqua in bacini alti)	It can be a good solution in cases where this is possible (Può essere un'ottima soluzione nei casi nei quali ciò sia possibile)

Figure 4.4.8. WETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 5

In summary, the agenda was:

- Brief Sol2H2O project presentation;
- What have we learned from the discussions held in Portugal, Italy, and Spain;
- Contribute to a joint vision on how to foster water-energy related applications of water treatment and desalination technology;
- Propose concrete collaborations: cooperation goals, R&D facilities and services, R&D needs, possible funding avenues;

- Become part of a technology developer/supplier community: companies' presentations;
- Contributions to an action plan.

Following the discussion, the contributions to an action plan were collected (Figure 4.4.4):

International Water Energy Symposium, 10.07.2025

Action Plan

solar driven solutions / brine mining

- design of overall treatment line must be optimized: pressure recovery, optimal location of intakes, promote reducing of fouling
- tenders must influence not only CAPEX but also stress quality of design (possibly over OPEX results and lifetime)
- brine mining: consider legal aspects and reduction of bureaucracy
- brine mining: production of a valuable byproduct needs to be able to identify a specific market, market requirements and legal/regulatory (quality) requirements
- regulation must keep pace with innovation: e.g. brine mining products, uses w/ biotechnology
- combination with biotechnology
- exploit potential of saline gradients in energy production

International Water Energy Symposium, 10.07.2025

Action Plan

solar driven solutions / brine mining

- technology barrier in RE integration: conventional RO plants are not as flexible as a solar-driven operation would require → stand-alone operation PV/RO: storage? membrane pressure oscillation
- Economic figures about brine mining are needed - make clear how much it costs and values (demonstrate that economic figures are promising)
- Barriers to bring products to the market - depends on purity of minerals; integrated approach, case-specific, need to see what can be recovered and sold
- Brine-mining plants designed to produce Mg for example would be economically viable instead of using it as a way to recover it from the desalination brines - not a solution since we need to address the issue of the brine disposal, however it is better to consider it since the design of the project

Action Plan

solar driven solutions / brine mining

- Advantage to couple with existing desal plants is that we have already the concentrated brine
- Need to consider the space needed for brine valorization - usually not addressed
- Space is also a limitation to coupling with renewable energy sources
- Energy communities concept involving desalination plants can be a solution? It can be a solution, but is not contemplated in the policies
- Added-value of the products as minerals recovered from the brines
- Regulation imposing higher recovery plants fostering also brine valorization could increase the CAPEX and impact on LCOW – it will be compulsory, desalination needs to be decarbonized and tackle the brine produced
- At the moment this would impact the water costs? Maybe we can reduce the water costs

Action Plan

solar driven solutions / brine mining

- It is really dependent on the chemicals lacking or that can be produced on site - independence from external suppliers, case-dependent - costs of chemicals, energy costs, difficulties in chemicals supply, CO2 cost - variables needed to be into account for the calculation
- need for “boundary conditions” study on viability of “advanced desalination plants”: high RR / low GHG

Action Plan

wastewater treatment plants / wastewater for irrigation

- no big technological constrains
- lack of infrastructure to distribute treated wastewater → need to understand economic viability conditions
- concept of “water communities” as in energy?
- opportunities/challenges w/ new EU Directive → check overlaps/mismatch between use and discharge directives
- dissemination of R&D results on the quality (contamination / nutritional value) of wastewater irrigated crops
- **in Murcia ca 90% irrigation water is reclaimed water** (treated wastewater)
- in Alentejo also reclaimed water is used for irrigation but not “formally” (i.e. not publicized)

Action Plan

wastewater treatment plants / wastewater for irrigation

- energy efficiency has been driven by reduction of energy costs
- adoption of ternary / quaternary treatments for emerging contaminants is economically challenging in ww treatment plants
- possibly emerging contaminants (when possible) should be addressed at their source (e.g. hospitals)
 - in Denmark an “opposite” conclusion was reached: hospitals are not a main source of emerging contaminants; major source lies on the population (distributed)
 - similar results in Belgium
- possibly action in hospitals might have higher impact on resistant-bacteria mitigation

Figure 4.4.4. WETSymp International Day conclusions: contributions to an Action Plan

After the symposium, a satisfaction survey was presented to the participants (by the end of the event, and sent by email to allow further answers), 13 answers were received (Appendix 9). The results show that 76,9% of the participants who answered the survey were totally satisfied with the symposium (Figure 4.4.5), and that the WETSymp corresponded to their expectations (100%). Participants working in the three countries represented on the Sol2H2O consortium attended (Portugal, Italy and Spain), which was one of the objectives (Figure 4.4.6) to have a more European view on the debate, but there were also at least one participant who works in another European country (France, verified from the registration emails).

To the question “Do you see an opportunity in the technological solutions presented? If so, to what extent?”, participants answered:

- *“Right now, brine mining is integrated into RO plants where it is economically viable”;*
- *“Yes, all proposed technologies have a nice perspective for growth and implementation”;*
- *“All solutions presented are interesting, although much work is still required to proceed. TRLs need to increase, but all solutions regarding PV, brine mining, and pumping are a major opportunity to be explored.”;*
- *“Yes”;*
- *“Yes, at semi-industrial level”;*
- *“Yes, further research focused on these issues may help overcome the current barriers.”;*
- *“The opportunity is, in my opinion, in the technologies applied for brine valorisation, because this approach could be addressed also toward many agroindustrial streams characterised by high salt concentrations in a perspective of circular bioeconomy”;*
- *“Yes, about the possibility of ZLD technologies”.*

2. Overall, how satisfied are you with the Sol2H2O WETSymp experience? (1 - strongly unsatisfied ... 5 - strongly satisfied)

13 respostas

Figure 4.4.5. WETSymp Satisfaction survey (overall satisfaction)

8. Country in which you work:

13 respostas

Figure 4.4.6. WETSymp Satisfaction survey (country)

5. CONCLUSIONS

Fostering Sol2H2O's objective 4. "To enhance the networking of UEvora in scientific and Industry fora, by means of disseminating the Widening RI services among Industry", the Regional Specialization Fora, Water-Energy Strategy Symposium and Water-Energy Transition Symposium activities herein reported have been designed as measures to maximize Sol2H2O's impact at the 4Helix level: Academia, Policy Makers, Industry, and Civil Society.

These events foster the project's outreach at regional (Regional Specialization Fora), national (Water-Energy Strategy Symposium) and international levels (Water-Energy Transition Symposium), as taken from the perspective of the Widening partner: national and regional levels refer to the widening partner, UÉvora, thus referring to Portugal and the Alentejo region; the international level, on the other hand, allowed for the participation of stakeholders from the Consortium countries, implying the presence of participants from Portugal, Italy and Spain.

Aiming at creating a vision on what could be a regional ecosystem enabling the development and deployment of Sol2H2O related technological solutions, the four editions of the Regional Specialization Fora already organized (a last edition is pending to close to project end) reflect the meagre industrial capabilities, in the region, in Sol2H2O related value chains, with participation in the RSF editions dominated by policy related actors. The adhesion gathered in the Fora editions, which can be considered "Good", registering ever new attendants.

At the national level, the Water-Energy Strategy Symposium gathered a total of 55 attendants, standing for an "Excellent" attendance level, and included in its scope:

- the presentation of Sol2H2O technological solutions;
- their role in the decarbonization objectives of both the National Energy and Climate Plan and the European 2050 Energy Roadmap objectives;
- National Industrial capacities;
- alternative R&I work, competitor technological concepts, regulatory environment and targeted markets;
- Presentations and speeches by both the Sol2H2O Consortium, Civil Society, Policy and Industrial actors.

One of the contents raising special attention among the audience was that related to the value chain coverage, at both regional and national levels, of Sol2H2O Beyond SoA technologies, from which important conclusions could be drawn:

- at the regional level, Sol2H2O related value chains can be covered by existing companies at a scarce 19% level regarding installation activities, at 40% regarding O&M activities, and no capabilities can be found at the manufacturing activities level;
- at the national level, these values rise to 53%, at manufacturing, and 100% at both installation and O&M levels.

In line with the conclusions drawn from the Regional Strategy Fora, this study rendered clear that an engagement of industrial actors around Sol2H2O technological solutions is likely to benefit from a national scoped partnership. This same initiative has been the scope for discussion in an extraordinary national gathering, within the scope of the 2024 European Desalination Society Conference held, coincidentally, in Porto.

The satisfaction survey presented to the audience after the Symposium, besides allowing us to conclude on the interest of this initiative, provided important feedback on the question “Do you see an opportunity in the technological solutions presented? If so, to what extent?”, to which participants' answers included:

- “Harnessing solar energy”;
- “Yes, optimising water and energy systems without dissociating one from the other.”;
- “Yes, mining brine from desalination plants can be an opportunity”;
- “Yes, use of desalinated water”;
- “Yes, but with the inherent difficulties of introducing systems that aren't mastered by the big industries.”;
- “Since we will never have a technology with zero environmental impact, I believe it is of the utmost importance to exploit the natural resources we have, and the combination of solar energy and desalination comes as a contribution to meeting a human need. In fact, as a great thinker would say, ‘One small step for man, one giant leap for mankind’, and another great sage who states that the principle of wisdom is: acquire it, and use everything you have to acquire understanding. This is to say that there are no small discoveries, but great beginnings. And yes, I think we are facing the beginning of a new cycle of intrusion, development and expansion of what the human mind is capable of developing. I realise that I'm not making much of a contribution in academic terms, but for that, I know you're doing your best and you'll do great things in that direction.”;
- “Yes, the desalination plant solution is a solution for the future.”;
- “A huge opportunity”;
- “Environmental sustainability”.

Finally, the international Water-Energy Transition Symposium, built upon a common framework of discussion, in each of the Consortium countries, gathering a specific group of relevant stakeholders around five specific questions:

- What kind of barriers to wastewater treatment and reuse for irrigation might be found by water management or water technology development companies?
- How can we overcome these barriers?
- What kind of challenges should be overcome for a real market implementation of ZLD solutions?
- What solutions (technological, economic, political/regulatory, environmental, social) do you propose for ZLD from the industry side?

- How could water storage be a solution for energy storage strategies in the case of large-scale renewable energy systems?

gathered a total of 48 attendants (34 of which external to Sol2H2O Consortium), on what can be regarded as a “Good” result. Dominated by Industry stakeholders, this discussion enabled the Consortium not only to have a broad vision on the most relevant approaches to the challenges identified in the questions to the stakeholders, in each country but also to draw a number of concrete actions for the ensuing promotion of Sol2H2O technological solutions and their market uptake.

These actions include, on the water desalination/brine mining side:

- due consideration of solar integration in the design stage of desalination plants;
- clarification of regulatory aspects of brine mining;
- the need for a clear roadmap of brine mining byproducts, concentration routes and byproduct commercial value;
- space requirements in brine mining operations;
- need/potential to develop “water communities” concept, following the already existing energy communities in the energy field;
- enforcement of higher recovery ratios in public desalination plant tenders, as to promote brine valorization approaches,

and, on the water treatment side:

- the lack of distribution infrastructure for the use of treated water for irrigation purposes;
- the need for dissemination of R&D results on the quality of crops irrigated with treated wastewater;
- the need to study the benefits of ternary/quaternary treatments closer to the major sources of emerging contaminants.

The results obtained in each of the events, showing a good adhesion by the corresponding target audiences, enabled the Sol2H2O Consortium to draw significant conclusions, to draw an action plan for ensuing actions and fully met Sol2H2O’s objective 4. “To enhance the networking of UEvora in scientific and Industry fora, by means of disseminating the Widening RI services among Industry”.

An important outcome of the discussions held at both regional and national levels on the Widening Partner side was the discussion initiated with an extraordinary national gathering, included in the program of the European Desalination Society 2024, held in Porto.

The discussion focused on the possibility of creating an Association for Desalination and Wastewater Reuse – Alternative Water Resources, which gathered a clear interest from those present.

In the aftermath of this gathering, a meeting to continue the discussion regarding the creation of a Portuguese association for alternative water resources was held in Évora (11th July), addressing the following main topics: (i) Mission; (ii) Objectives; (iii) Lines of Action; (iv) Management.

At the start of the meeting, given the presence of colleagues who had not attended the first meeting in Porto, a proposal was presented for the creation of an association focused on desalination and water reuse in Portugal. The example of Asociación Española de Desalación y Reutilización (AEDyR) was introduced, highlighting certain parallels and potential lessons. However, it was emphasised that in Portugal, the focus should not be solely on desalination, but rather on a broader approach to the sustainable management of water resources with a technological focus. This resulted in the proposed Mission of the association:

Mission: To contribute to the sustainable management of water resources by promoting the use of alternative water resources, such as the reuse of treated wastewater and seawater desalination, through an integrated approach aligned with the water-energy-food-ecosystem nexus.

The major Lines of Action were discussed: Valorization of water resources; Water production as a by-product of brine mining; Promotion of innovative technological approaches; Development of

documents with political and strategic impact; Environmental education. The association should function as a coordination forum for its members' interests, and it was considered important to promote communication and interaction among members.

From this exchange of ideas, the following Objectives emerged:

- To foster research and innovation in technological solutions for the valorization and circular use of alternative water resources (wastewater and seawater). However, the Association will not directly conduct R&D (to avoid competing with the work of its members);
- To promote the exchange and dissemination of information related to these technologies among its members;
- To act as a public forum for information, documentation, and environmental education;
- To support and promote the creation of standardized technical specifications and procedures;
- To cooperate and collaborate with public administration and other public or private organizations (national, EU-level, or international) on issues related to legislation, governance, regulation, and public policy;
- To promote training and technical certification activities for professionals in the water production and treatment sector regarding the use of new technological solutions;
- To promote energy efficiency and the decarbonization of water production and treatment processes;
- To implement technology demonstration activities within its areas of work.

The Lines of Action were then examined, and the feasibility of realistically fulfilling these activities, given available resources and capabilities, was questioned. The proposed lines of action are detailed below:

- Coordination and organization of congresses and technical meetings;
- Organization of seminars and training courses;
- Technical assistance in this field to public or private, national or international institutions;
- Conducting specific studies and projects to generate the information needed for industrial development, public policy planning, or legislative and regulatory proposals;
- Preparation of documents, databases, and web portals;
- Integration into supranational organizations with similar goals;
- Promotion of R&D and demonstration activities carried out by its members.

The institutional model was debated, including the possibility of integrating the association as a specialized commission within the Portuguese Association of Water Resources (in Portuguese, Associação Portuguesa de Recursos Hídricos, APRH). However, concerns were raised that such integration could dilute the goals of the new association, compromising its visibility and impact. The new association would have an inherently technological focus, differentiating it from APRH, which is more oriented towards water management, governance, and policy. A note of caution was raised: if a new association is created, it should therefore avoid overlap with APRH (e.g., in name, mission, objectives, etc.).

It was suggested that a database be created with relevant entities, including national companies that are active in or could benefit from the association's work, as well as other relevant stakeholders.

Finally, the concept of "Water Communities" was introduced, inspired by the existing "Energy Communities," as a potential future model of operation.

A new meeting was scheduled for September, given the interest in the subject, and is proposed to take place in Porto during the week of September 22–26. Until then, should be in place the process of engaging teams focused on the following topics:

- Economic data on brine mining — demonstrating its economic viability;
- Studies on the feasibility of advanced desalination plants (e.g., boundary conditions — high recovery rate (RR) /low greenhouse gas emissions (GHG));

- Lack of infrastructure for distributing treated wastewater → need to understand the conditions necessary for its economic feasibility;
- Concept of "Water Communities," similar to the "Energy Communities."

6. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Communications Management Plan

The *Communications Management Plan* helps to ensure that all project stakeholders have the information they need to perform their roles throughout the project. It defines and documents the communication items' content, format, frequency, audience and expected results. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive in Google Drive. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be saved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A and B) <GrantAgreement-101079305-Sol2H2O-1.pdf>	Project folder
3	Communications Management Plan <[16.I.PM2-Template.v3].Communications_Management_Plan.(Sol2H2O).(31-05-2023).(v3.0)>	Project Folder
5	Deliverables acceptance plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v.1>	Project Folder
6	Deliverables acceptance note <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SOL2H2O.26-05-2023.v1.0.xls>	Project Folder
7	Deliverables acceptance Checklist <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v1.0>	Project Folder
8	Regional Specialization Fora folder	Project Folder
9	Water-Energy Strategy Symposium folder	Project Folder
10	Water-Energy Transition Symposium folder	Project Folder

APPENDIX 2: ATTENDANCE LISTS

- **Regional Specialization Forum #1**
- **Regional Specialization Forum #2**
- **Regional Specialization Forum #3**
- **Regional Specialization Forum Palermo**
- **Water-Energy Strategy Symposium**
- **National Water Energy Strategy Symposium**
- **Water-Energy Transition Symposium - International Day**

APPENDIX 3: WESSYMP SATISFACTION SURVEY

Género

9 respostas

- Feminino
- Masculino
- Outro
- Prefiro não responder

Idade

9 respostas

- 18 - 30 anos
- 31 - 40
- 41 - 50
- 51 - 60
- > 60

Qual o seu setor?

9 respostas

- Universidade
- Organização de investigação e tecnologia pública
- Indústria
- Organização de investigação e tecnologia privada

Numa escala de 1 a 5, como classifica a sua satisfação geral com o Water-Energy Strategy Symposium?

9 respostas

Vê um oportunidade nas soluções tecnológicas apresentadas?

Se sim, em que medida?

9 respostas

Aproveitamento solar

Sim, na optimização dos sistema hídricos e energéticos sem estarem dissociados um do outro.

Sim. A mineração de salmoura das Dessalinizadoras pode ser uma oportunidade

Sim, uso de água dessalinizada

Sim, mas com as dificuldades inerentes à introdução de sistemas que não dominados pelas grandes indústrias.

Na medida em que de facto nunca teremos uma tecnologia com zero impacto ambiental, creio ser de suma importância explorar os recursos naturais que temos, a junção da energia solar e dessalinização, vêm como um contributo à suprir uma necessidade humana. Na verdade, como diria um grande pensador "Um pequeno passo para o homem, um grande salto para a humanidade" e ainda outro grande sábio que afirma que o princípio da sabedoria é: adquira-a, e use tudo o que você possui para adquirir entendimento. Isso para afirmar que não há pequenas descobertas, mas sim grandes inicio. E sim, penso estarmos diante do inicio de um novo ciclo de intrusão, desenvolvimento e expansão daquilo que a mente humano está apta para desenvolver.

Sei que não estou a ser muito contributiva em termos académicos, mas para isso, sei que estão a dar o vosso melhor e grandes coisas farão nesse sentido.

Sim, a solução da dessalinizadora é uma solução de futuro.

Uma enorme oportunidade

Sustentabilidade ambiental

O Water-Energy Strategy Symposium correspondeu às suas expetativas?

9 respostas

● Sim
● Não

Se respondeu "não" na pergunta anterior, diga-nos porquê:

0 respostas

Ainda não existem respostas a esta pergunta.

Deixe aqui sugestões/comentários:

1 resposta

Parabéns a equipa.

Tomei conhecimento de que os dados que voluntariamente e anonimamente disponibilizo são da responsabilidade da coordenação do projeto Sol2H2O (investigador responsável: Dr. Pedro Horta) e serão armazenados até ao final dos projetos (2025), numa pasta de acesso restrito aos parceiros Sol2H2O. Os contactos só serão partilhados exclusivamente aos parceiros Sol2H2O (UÉvora, UNIPA, ITC e CIEMAT) caso figure a autorização para o efeito.

 Copiar gráfico

9 respostas

● Sim

APPENDIX 4: WETSYPM IDEATION SCRIPT

Sol2H2O - Ideation

SCRIPT

WASTE WATER BARRIERS

What types of barriers to wastewater treatment and reuse for irrigation might water management or water technology development companies encounter?

1. Please write three ideas, one advantage per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes do answer.
2. Turn *private mode on*.
3. Start *5 min timer on*.
4. Turn *private mode off* to reveal the answers.
5. Group similar answers.
6. Start *10 min timer on*.
7. Each participant must vote in his/her three favourite ideas. You only have 5 min to vote.
8. **Start voting**, adjust the voting area.
9. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase them, if necessary.
10. Start *10 min timer on*.
11. Rewrite the three main ideas in the bottom board.

WASTE WATER SOLUTIONS

How can we overcome the previous barriers?

1. Copy the three most voted answers in the previous question to the top of this board.
2. Please write three solutions to the previous challenges, one solution per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes do answer.
3. Turn *private mode on*.
4. Start *5 min timer on*.
5. Turn *private mode off* to reveal the answers.
6. Group similar answers.
7. Start *10 min timer on*.
8. Each participant must vote in his/her three favourite ideas. You only have 5 min to vote.
9. **Start voting**, adjust the voting area.
10. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase, if necessary.
11. Start *10 min timer on*.
12. Rewrite the three main ideas in the bottom board.

15 minutes break!!

ZLD CHALLENGES

What challenges must be overcome to successfully implement ZLD solutions in the market?

1. Please write three ideas, one idea per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes do answer.
2. Turn *private mode on*.
3. Start *5 min timer on*.
4. Turn *private mode off* to reveal the answers.
5. Group similar answers.
6. Start *10 min timer on*.
7. Each participant must vote in his/her three favourite ideas. You only have 5 min to vote.
8. **Start voting**, adjust the voting area.
9. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase, if necessary.
10. Start *10 min timer on*.
11. Rewrite the three main ideas in the bottom board.

ZLD SOLUTIONS

What solutions (technological, economic, regulatory, environmental, or social) do you propose to overcome the challenges of ZLD?

1. Copy the three most voted answers in the previous question to the top of this board.
2. Please write three solutions to the previous challenges, one solution per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes do answer.
3. *Turn **private mode on**.*
4. *Start **5 min timer on**.*
5. *Turn **private mode off** to reveal the answers.*
6. Group similar answers.
7. *Start **10 min timer on**.*
8. Each participant must vote in his/her three favourite ideas. You only have 5 min to vote.
9. ***Start voting**, adjust the voting area.*
10. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase, if necessary.
11. *Start **10 min timer on**.*
12. Rewrite the three main ideas in the bottom board.

WATER STORAGE

How could water storage be a solution for energy storage strategies in the case of large-scale renewable energy systems?

1. Please write three ideas, one idea per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes do answer.
2. *Turn **private mode on**.*
3. *Start **5 min timer on**.*
4. *Turn **private mode off** to reveal the answers.*
5. Group similar answers.
6. *Start **10 min timer on**.*
7. Each participant must vote in his/her three favourite ideas. You only have 5 min to vote.
8. ***Start voting**, adjust the voting area.*
9. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase, if necessary.
10. *Start **10 min timer on**.*
11. Rewrite the three main ideas in the bottom board.

APPENDIX 5: WETSYPM IDEATION INSTRUCTIONS

Sol2H2O - Ideation

EDITING

1. Open the Miro Board, following the links:

[English](#)

[Portuquese](#)

[Italian \(to be translated\)](#)

[Spanish \(to be translated\)](#)

2. To edit the text, select the table or text box. On the menu, press and hold the locker to unlock the text box. Write your text.
3. After writing, select the table/text box and press the lock in the menu.

SHARING THE BOARD

1. Open the Miro Board, following the links:

[English](#)

[Portuquese](#)

[Italian \(to be translated\)](#)

[Spanish \(to be translated\)](#)

2. Make sure that the board is Public. Go to share (top right). Select **can edit** in copy guest link and **editor** in Anyone with the link.

3. To share the board, click Copy board link and paste to share.

ACCESSING THE BOARD

1. When the participants open the link they will find the text box below. It is recommended that the participants write their names to identify themselves on the board, but it is optional. Write participant's name and press continue.

- The participants don't have to write their email. They can just press Enter board now.

INSTRUCTIONS AND TOOLS DURING THE DYNAMICS

- Ask participants to go to board **1. Waste water barriers**.
- Read the question to the participants: *What types of barriers to wastewater treatment and reuse for irrigation might water management or water technology development companies encounter?*
- Tell the participants that they must write **three ideas, each one in a different post it**.
- Before the participants start answering, make sure the board is in private mode. Go to the tools menu on the top right (see below) and select Private mode. Select Go on private mode for all. Now, the participants can only read their own post its.

- To answer, the participants must drag a post it to the white board and write on it. Before starting the dynamics, make sure they know how to do it.
- Now, we will start. The participants have **5 min** to write their ideas. Start the 5 min timer (on the left of the board).
- When the time is over, reveal the answers. Click in the closed-eye post it on the top right and press End for all and then Turn off for all. After 3 seconds all post its are shown.

- Present the ideas and organize the post its by grouping similar answers. Stack the post-its with similar ideas, making sure they are perfectly aligned (otherwise, they will count more than once during the voting).
- Each participant must vote in the best three ideas. Click on Open voting on the left of the board (3 votes; 5 min). Make sure that all post its are inside the voting area. If necessary, adjust the voting area by dragging the corners. Press start in the voting window.
- Drag the three most voted ideas to the bottom part of the board. Discuss and rephrase, if necessary.

11. Repeat for questions 2 – 5.

APPENDIX 6: PORTUGUESE DAY RESULTS

Sol2H2O

Abordagem tecnológica Sol2H2O:
Zero Liquid Discharge

1. TRATAMENTO DE ÁGUA RESIDUAIS - DESAFIOS

Que desafios podem enfrentar as empresas de gestão de água ou de desenvolvimento tecnológico no tratamento de águas residuais e na reutilização para fins de irrigação? (duas ideias, uma ideia por post it)

Sol2H2O

Abordagem tecnológica Sol2H2O:
Zero Liquid Discharge

2. TRATAMENTO DE ÁGUA RESIDUAIS - SOLUÇÕES

Sticky stack

Como podemos superar os desafios anteriores?
(duas ideias, uma ideia por post it)

Desafios (copiar os três mais votados do quadro anterior):

Desafios sociais: aceitação pública, tanto por parte dos agricultores quanto por parte dos consumidores

custo da tecnologia

Transporte da água tratada para o uso final

Comunicação e transparência

Leonel Alegre

Controlo analítico frequente

Rui Sequeira

Celeridade no processo burocrático

Rui Sequeira

Investigação para desenvolvimento de novas tecnologias

Rui Sequeira

Aproveitar economias de escala

Rui Sequeira

Tecnologia com soluções baseadas na natureza

Edoardo

Custos: Eventual subsidiação.

Rui Sequeira

Gestão territorial

Rui Sequeira

Transporte único para água reutilizada

Rui Sequeira

Campanhas comunicação

Rui Sequeira

Enfoque na "Água" e não na origem da mesma

Mais informação e transparência nos processos.

Rui Sequeira

Desafios sociais: Campanhas de sensibilização com demonstração de resultados

Rui Sequeira

Ações de divulgação no espaço rural

Rui Sequeira

Foco na comunicação clara e direcionada ao público alvo

Rui Sequeira

Gestão integrada das várias origens de água, com diversificação de usos em locais de sistemas descentralizados qd aplicável/conveniente

Rui Sequeira

Comunicação e transparência

Leonel Alegre

Gestão territorial (5 votos)

Investigação para desenvolvimento de novas tecnologias (4 votos)

Rui Sequeira

Sol2H2O

Abordagem tecnológica Sol2H2O:

Zero Liquid Discharge

3. ZLD - DESAFIOS

Que desafios devem ser superados para implementar com sucesso soluções ZLD no mercado?
(duas ideias, uma ideia por post it)

Sol2H2O

Abordagem tecnológica Sol2H2O:
Zero Liquid Discharge

4. ZLD - SOLUÇÕES

Que soluções (tecnológicas, económicas, regulatórias, ambientais ou sociais) **propõe para superar os desafios associados a ZLD?**
(duas ideias, uma ideia por post it)

Desafios (copiar os três mais votados do quadro anterior):

Viabilidade económica do projeto em larga escala

Reaproveitamento da salmoura final - Potássio, Boro, cloreto de Sódio

destino final da salmoura - área necessária para a evaporação à escala real (3 votos)

Estímulo à formação de consórcios industriais

Associação de potenciais utilizadores/Economia de escala

Estudo de mercado para os produtos retirados da salmoura

Integrar a investigação das ZLD solutions com a investigação de produtos para usos industriais ou comerciais, ex. detergentes para identificar possíveis usos

Parcerias com empresas/setores que possam utilizar os produtos resultantes da salmoura

Integrar produção de água com soluções de uso de salmouras

Criação de normas claras para o destino final da salmoura

Investigar soluções de evaporação rápida/concentração de calor...

Investigação com vista à inovação e Desenvolvimento de ações para aproveitamento da salmoura

I&D relativo a utilização de solar térmico para promover a evaporação

Integrar a investigação das ZLD solutions com a investigação de produtos (para usos industriais ou comerciais, ex. detergentes) para identificar possíveis usos

Investigar soluções de evaporação rápida/concentração de calor...

Estudo de mercado para os produtos retirados da salmoura

Sol2H2O

Abordagem tecnológica Sol2H2O:
Zero Liquid Discharge

5. ARMAZENAMENTO DE ÁGUA

Como pode o armazenamento de água ser uma solução para o armazenamento de energia no caso de sistemas de energia renovável em larga escala?
(duas ideias, uma ideia por post it)

Promoção de sistemas de armazenamento reversíveis

Locais de armazenamento geo-estratégicos para fins energéticos.

Armazenamento em cascata

Locais ambientalmente mais favoráveis

Armazenamento de água em altitude seguida de turbinagem

Armazenamento em locais elevados de forma a poder ser libertada por gravidade.

Promoção de sistemas de armazenamento reversíveis

Locais de armazenamento geo-estratégicos para fins energéticos.

APPENDIX 7: ITALIAN DAY RESULTS

Sol2H2O

Sol2H2O technological approach:

Zero Liquid Discharge

2. WASTE WATER SOLUTIONS

How can we overcome the previous barriers?
(three ideas; one idea per post it)

Barriers (copy the three most voted from the previous board):

Opinione pubblica contro l'uso di acque reflue

cost of treated water vs. willingness to pay by end user

regulations sometimes conflicting

Campagne informativa che spieghino come l'acqua trattata sia sicura specialmente anche in contesti di scarsa disponibilità idrica

incentivi economici sull'utilizzo dell'acqua trattata

Distribute water cost over all the water used regardless of the origin

accordi di settore per uso acqua trattata

riutilizzo dell'acqua sì, ma chi è disposto ad autorizzarlo, necessita di quadri normativi più chiari

Structural revision of the laws (towards simplification)

Re-Scholar EU: by books and not weapons

semplificazione legislativa e amministrativa

informazione e divulgazione

Information

Bonus encouraging the use of this treated waste water

Campagne informative che spieghino come l'acqua trattata sia sicura specialmente anche in contesti di scarsa disponibilità idrica

incentivi economici sull'utilizzo dell'acqua trattata

Structural revision of the laws (towards simplification)

3. ZLD CHALLENGES

What challenges must be overcome to successfully implement ZLD solutions in the market?
(three ideas; one idea per post it)

utilizzo di parecchia energia spesso da fonti non rinnovabili, risulterebbe a volte poco sostenibile

Obtain products and specifics with a purity that meet the market

Making the brine valorization process economic competitive

4. ZLD SOLUTIONS

What solutions (technological, economic, regulatory, environmental, or social) do you propose to overcome the challenges of ZLD?
(three ideas; one idea per post it)

Barriers (copy the three most voted from the previous board):

utilizzo di parecchia energia spesso da fonti non rinnovabili, risulterebbe a volte poco sostenibile

Obtain products and specifics with a purity that meet the market

Making the brine valorization process economic competitive

premiabilità per progetti che includono soluzioni ZLD

Creare dei mercati virtuali di incontro tra domanda e offerta

imporre vincoli legislativi che obblighino alla valorizzazione di almeno un'aliquota della salamoia prodotta

5. WATER STORAGE

Sticky stack

How could water storage be a solution for energy storage strategies in the case of large-scale renewable energy systems?

(three ideas; one idea per post it)

può essere un'ottima soluzione nei casi nei quali ciò sia possibile

conversione in energia potenziale, l'energia elettrica può essere utilizzata per il pompaggio dell'acqua in bacini alti

Incrementare la produzione durante le ore di picco di disponibilità di energia rinnovabile

lo scarico della salamoia da impianti di dissalazione potrebbe generare energia tramite una turbina

Soluzione eccellente in particolar modo nelle realtà dove sono presenti impianti di dissalazione

L'accumulo in quota presso laghi e invasi potrebbe essere una buona strategia ma prevede la messa a sistema di moti stakeholders

Accumulare acqua prodotta (con FER) in eccesso anziché energia

utilizzo delle fonti rinnovabili (fotovoltaiche) per produzione successiva di energia idroelettrica (turbine)

Incrementare la produzione durante le ore di picco di disponibilità di energia rinnovabile

conversione in energia potenziale, l'energia elettrica può essere utilizzata per il pompaggio dell'acqua in bacini alti

può essere un'ottima soluzione nei casi nei quali ciò sia possibile

APPENDIX 8: SPANISH DAY RESULTS

SOL2H20 Funded by the European Union

Estrategia Nexo Agua-Energía
Workshop

Auditorio Adán Martín, S/C de Tenerife

JUN 23
16:00-19:30

EVENTO PRESENCIAL

DEBATE

Mentimeter

31

¿Qué tipo de barreras encuentra para el tratamiento y la reutilización de aguas para el riego?

Barreras administrativas	Regulatorio	Administrativas y control analítico que no discrimina entre la dimensión de los sistemas.	La percepción social
8 Popular	4	4	3
Normativa, autorizaciones administrativas,	Inversión e infraestructura	Normativa, Exigencias que no tienen otras fuentes de agua	No hay incentivos
3	2	2	2

Mentimeter

7 23

¿Qué tipo de barreras encuentra para el tratamiento y la reutilización de aguas para el riego ?

La eliminación total de contaminantes emergentes y microplásticos

2

No se trabaja la segregación en origen

2

Al alcance de la infraestructura de distribución

2

Precio del agua

1

Percepción del usuario

1

El alto coste de opex y capex.

1

Regulación muy estricta.

1

Concurrencia con el reuso no controlado

1

¿Qué tipo de barreras encuentra para el tratamiento y la reutilización de aguas para el riego ?

El tiempo que requieren las autorizaciones ambientales y administrativas

1

Variabilidad de alimentación

No se cubren los costes

Ninguna

Desconfianza de resultados

El coste que tienen los controles de calidad del agua para pequeños caudales de vertido

Que no se tome agua gratis de los pozos

Sociales, regulatorias, económicas

¿Qué tipo de barreras encuentra para el tratamiento y la reutilización de aguas para el riego?

Las ttabas burocráticas y dificultades tecnológicas y económicas en la operación.

Nueva regulación y adaptación
Calidad muy exigente según cultivos
Conocimiento y formación de comunidades de regentes
Coste en comparación con otras fuentes
Concienciación

Voluntad política

Falta de información por parte de la ciudadanía.

Producción ecológica

Abordar los planes de gestión de riesgo que propone la normativa y ofrecer transparencia informativa.

Mejora en la gobernanza.
Comunicación social.

¿Cómo podemos superar estas barreras? - Identificar soluciones especialmente para las aguas regeneradas

Mayor comunicación social

5

Popular

Con políticas y educación que pongan realmente en valor las aguas regeneradas

4

Incentivos económicos

3

Planes diferentes para los grandes y pequeños sistemas

3

Formación y concienciación

3

Implicación de todos los agentes. Facilitar la tramitación y dotar de recursos a las administraciones

3

Mejorando el marco normativo

3

Divulgación y formación constante desde la base

2

¿Cómo podemos superar estas barreras? - Identificar soluciones especialmente para las aguas regeneradas

Potenciar los PGRAR 2	Gestión de riesgos y transparencia informativa con participación de usuarios. 2	Potencia terciarios en EDAR 1	Validación mediante estudios de investigación a gran escala 1
Pedagogía, publicidad vía congresos, charlas, jornadas, etc. 1	Adaptar los controles analíticos al caudal reutilizado. 1	Incentivo al vertido cero 1	Desarrollando normativas regionales, que contemplen la realidad local, bajo unos mínimos comunes. 1

¿Cómo podemos superar estas barreras? - Identificar soluciones especialmente para las aguas regeneradas

Avanzando en el desarrollo de las infraestructuras en paralelo a la información a la población 1	Una administración que aúne todos los ámbitos regulatorios con asesoramiento técnico y financiero 1	Reducción de costes	Políticos y funcionarios concienciados
Con charlas explicativas	Compartiendo soluciones exitosas en otras partes del mundo	Divulgación al público	Marco regulatorio claro

¿Cómo podemos superar estas barreras? - Identificar soluciones especialmente para las aguas regeneradas

Disminuir las trabas burocráticas, el papel pasa por mas manos y todos le ponen una linea.

Fomentar información y formación de los agricultores

Medir huella ambiental del agua puesta en la red

Investigacion

Mejorar gobernanza. Comunicación social.

Incentivar la regeneración en actividades concretas.

Crear herramientas para recuperar los costes

Costes

¿Cómo podemos superar estas barreras? - Identificar soluciones especialmente para las aguas regeneradas

Económica , energético y medioambiental.

Integrar los usos ambientales en la planificación hidrológica.

¿Qué tipo de desafíos/barreras deberían superarse para una implementación real en el mercado de las soluciones ZLD?

¿Qué tipo de desafíos/barreras deberían superarse para una implementación real en el mercado de las soluciones ZLD?

¿Qué tipo de desafíos/barreras deberían superarse para una implementación real en el mercado de las soluciones ZLD?

Valorizar productos selectivos

1

La desconfianza de la utilidad real del concepto ZLD como solución genérica.

1

Concienciación de utilidad/necesidad

1

No hay auditorías de vertidos

Integración de renovables

No hay incentivos

Viabilidad económica

Rentabilidad económica

¿Qué tipo de desafíos/barreras deberían superarse para una implementación real en el mercado de las soluciones ZLD?

Falta de segregación de vertidos en origen, es decir le mezcla de vertidos.

Buscar un equilibrio entre el coste de inversión respecto al caudal recuperado

Reutilización segura de agua de secundario.

Reducir su huella de carbono

Experiencia y por tanto, coste.

Quizás el marco normativo ni lo permita

No verter, ¿por qué?

Son grandes volúmenes y no hay mercado para los subproductos

¿Qué tipo de desafíos/barreras deberían superarse para una implementación real en el mercado de las soluciones ZLD?

Proyectos pilotos de reutilización segura con agua de secundario.

El consumo energético

Análisis multicriterio para evaluar cuando llegar.

Establecimiento de proyectos pilotos estratégicos

Inversión en I+D+I y en desarrollo de infraestructuras

¿Qué soluciones (tecnológicas, económicas, políticas/regulatorias, ambientales, sociales) propone para implantar tecnología ZLD?

El ZLD no tiene porque ser un objetivo en todos los casos. Hay que analizarlos uno por uno.

5

Popular

Mayor esfuerzo en I+D+i

4

Incentivar economía circular

4

Análisis de materias primas críticas

3

Proyectos demostrativos que integren incentivos a la valorización

3

Identificar y buscar salida comercial a los productos recuperados

3

Hay que analizar caso por caso y de forma general estudiar si vale la pena la tecnología ZLD

3

Crear un censo de vertidos potencialmente valoriza les x islas/comarcas

2

¿Qué soluciones (tecnológicas, económicas, políticas/regulatorias, ambientales, sociales) propone para implantar tecnología ZLD?

Desarrollo de planes de inversión específicos por las Administraciones

2

Fomentar proyectos piloto de innovación tecnológica

1

Falicitar guías técnicas/administrativas para su implantación

1

Dotar los presupuestos de inversión necesarios. Pasar el coste a los usuarios

1

Integración de renovables

1

Concienciación social y medioambiental

1

Proyectos de pilotos de reutilización con agua de secundario.

1

Incentivar económicamente su implantación y la valorización de subproductos.

1

¿Qué soluciones (tecnológicas, económicas, políticas/regulatorias, ambientales, sociales) propone para implantar tecnología ZLD?

Proyectos piloto de soluciones basadas en la naturaleza.

1

Guía de tecnologías ZLD

1

Análisis multicriterio para evaluar cuando llegar

1

Concienciación social

Transferencia de obligación o venta de créditos

Aceptar un cierto vertido y no llegar siempre a vertido cero

Integrar en la planificación hidrológica barreras contra la intrusión marina con aguas regeneradas

Exenciones fiscales sobre el consumo de energía

¿Qué soluciones (tecnológicas, económicas, políticas/regulatorias, ambientales, sociales) propone para implantar tecnología ZLD?

La gestión del agua, producción, transporte y distribución, deben usarse como elementos de gestión de la demanda de energía eléctrica

Desarrollar proyectos con reservorios con diferencias de altura moderadas y gran caudal

¿Cómo podría, el almacenamiento de agua, ser la solución para las estrategias de almacenamiento de energía a gran escala?

Adaptando la desalación a la disponibilidad de energía renovable

9

Popular

Bombeo reversible

5

Bombes con el excedente de las EERR, acumulación en balsas y posterior turbinado para consumo local

5

Apostando por sistemas aislados que cubran la energía demandada en sitios concretos

2

En aquellos casos que se disponga de renovables para alimentar el ciclo hidroeléctrico

2

Esta mas que consolidado. Además puede resolver, con la misma infraestructura, problemas de falta de agua en cotas altas como es el caso de Tenerife

2

La gestión del agua, producción, transporte y distribución, deben usarse como elementos de gestión de la demanda de energía eléctrica

2

Se debería aprovechar como primera opción siempre que la geografía y el impacto ambiental lo permita.

1

¿Cómo podría, el almacenamiento de agua, ser la solución para las estrategias de almacenamiento de energía a gran escala?

Podría ser una parte de la solución, combinada con otras

1

Es una opción que dependerá de gran cantidad de factores

1

Teniendo espacio suficiente

1

Con un adecuado análisis técnico y ambiental de los casos concretos

1

Combinándolo con otras estrategias

1

Almacenamiento en aguas subterráneas

1

Gradiente salino

No es la única solución tecnológica pero su desarrollo en algunas islas es posible

¿Cómo podría, el almacenamiento de agua, ser la solución para las estrategias de almacenamiento de energía a gran escala?

Volver a los años 50-60 para ejecutar presas para centrales de reboteo.

El agua puede actuar como vector energético

Provechando condiciones naturales existentes

Análisis de la situación y usos compartidos.

En sistemas que sobre energía renovables y se necesite almacenar

APPENDIX 9: WETSYPM SATISFACTION SURVEY

1. How did you hear about this event?

13 respuestas

2. Overall, how satisfied are you with the Sol2H2O WETSymp experience? (1 - strongly unsatisfied ... 5 - strongly satisfied)

13 respuestas

3. Do you see an opportunity in the technological solutions presented?

If so, to what extent?

8 respuestas

- Right now, brine mining integrated into RO plants where it is economically viable
- yes, all proposed technologies have a nice perspective for growth and implementation
- All solutions presented are interesting, although much work is still required to proceed. TRLs need to increase, but all solutions regarding PV, brine mining, pumping are a major opportunity to be explored.
- Yes
- Yes, at semi-industrial level
- Yes, further research focused on these issues may help overcome the current barriers.

The opportunity is in my opinion in the technologies applied for brine valorization, because this approach could be addressed also toward many agroindustrial streams characterized by high salt concentrations in a perspective of circular bioeconomy

Yes, about the possibility of ZLD technologies

4. Did the Water-Energy Transition Symposium match your expectations?

13 respuestas

5. Gender:

13 respuestas

6. Age:

13 respuestas

7. Sector:
13 respostas

8. Country in which you work:
13 respostas

9. Do you have any suggestions?
1 resposta

I suggest to include in the analysis e in the deepenings of the research also the opportunity to apply the approach of valorization to different sectors of industry especially food industry

10. The data you voluntarily provide is the responsibility of the Sol2H2O project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored in a...o so. Images and sound will be taken at this event.
13 respostas

